

Analytical Study Of The Allama Iqbal Philosophy Of Perfect Man Under The Light Of Islamic Concept

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Abstract

Dr. Iqbal describes in his essay "Iqbal and Sufi" the attributes of a perfect believer as, "A perfect believer is that when a person recognizes his own inner, God is obtained through this ability and this is the sign of a noble human being. Iqbal considers Sufi a perfect man for this and perfect believer is an important part of his poetry. This concept is similar to the famous German thinker Nietzsche's concept of superhuman. The qualities and attributes of the perfect man that Iqbal has described in his poetry are very clear. Iqbal says that a perfect human being has all the qualities that are necessary to be a perfect human being. In the attributes of a good and true Muslim, along with believing in Allah Almighty and His Holy Prophet, he should have a high character. It should be a true reflection of the courage and truth in the gossip and character. In his opinion, the heart of a perfect human being has a soft and hard temper. Where it cools the heart, it hardens like steel. He shakes the rivers and streams. In addition to following the teachings of the Qur'an, a believer desires a horse and a sword, which he considers necessary. In Iqbal's opinion, a believing man is brave, he does not like to be defeated. He always wants martyrdom and his desired goal is martyrdom. Iqbal says that the desire for perfect man is never wrong. He says that a believer is identified in such a way that he never gets lost in the universe but the universes get lost in it. That is why the whole world is his legacy and he has power. According to Iqbal, the concept of Sufism is the basic concept that leads to success.

Introduction

Allama Iqbal made many topics a part of his poetry but one point around which all his poetry could be seen to revolve is the love of the Holy Prophet Muhammad Mustafa (PBUH) and all his thoughts on the teachings of Holy Quran and Sunnah of Prophet. According to one of the subjects of Allama Iqbal's thought is 'the man of the believer' whom he has also described in the light of Qur'an and Hadith. Dr. Muhammad Tahir-ul-Qadri writes, "Allama Iqbal in his speech has presented the idea of 'Mard-e-Momin'. Other Sufis and faqras have also used the terms 'perfect man' and 'faqir-kamal' for the man of faith. In the term of Faqr, the believer man, the perfect man, the perfect faqir, the man of Qalandar means the entity which is endowed with all the attributes of God and in which the manifestation of truth is enlightened, is the vicegerent of the Prophet and while performing his duties and guide him to the right path. The rank of the perfect human being is the highest place in poverty. There is no one higher than him. It would not be out of place to say that this time is the sum of all levels. Of all human beings, the most perfect and perfect human being is the perfect human being, the Holy Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him). After you, your deputies get this time through you. In Iqbal's view, success requires adherence to Islamic principles, and in this context, Iqbal views spirituality from one angle, as if he were setting himself up for it.

Fundamentally the Perfect Muslim or Man of Iqbal is a Sufi Muslim. He may possess alien qualities but his beginning and end are colored in the pattern of Sufism. Iqbal has propounded his philosophy based on Quranic ideas. He believes in the superiority of man based on piety. While Christianity, for example, degraded the status of man by making him a product of sin. But the concept among Muslims is that Allah Almighty makes man His vicegerent. The Holy Quran says, "He is who hath placed you as viceroy of the earth and hath exalted some of you in rank above others that He may try you by (the test of) that which He hath given you"¹

There are many such references in the Holy Quran which confirm Iqbal's belief in the suzerainty and perfectibility of Man. The status of man is very high, elevated, and sublime. He is capable of great achievements. With this recognition, Iqbal points out the course which will lead to the ideal perfection in other words, he has pointed out the qualities the wielder of which will be the Perfect Man. The status of Man in Islam is very high, for Iqbal the ideal is in the person of Muhammad the Prophet Peace Be Upon Him. The ultimate and final struggle of Man is towards that ideal to be perfect. The way is, no doubt, full of obstacles but the efforts of such a man remain unimpeded. He keeps on fighting, moving forward, onward, and upward. His ultimate destination

is to be found in his efforts and struggles. Talking about a man's life, agreeing with Bergson, Iqbal writes, "In the words of Bergson, I pass from state to state, I am warm or cold. I am merry or sad. I work or do nothing. I look at what is around me or I think of something else. Sensation, feelings, volitions, ideas, such are the changes into which my existence is divided and which color it in turns. I change, I change, then without ceasing'. Thus there is nothing static in my innerlife all is constant mobility, an unceasing flux of states, a perpetual flow in which there is no halt or resting place."ⁱⁱⁱ Hence the most prominent quality of the Perfect Man is to be always in action and static life is death. The very essence of life is change, movement, and dynamism. According to Iqbal this is inherent within and sprouts out in the without. The recognition of this single fact makes Man realize his position in this ever-changing universe. Iqbal rightly points out that this concept of change is not European or Bergsonian but it is purely Quranic. The concept of change is to be found in the philosophies of Heraclitus and the Stoics. But they talk about the cyclic repetitions, Iqbal does not agree with it as it is non-Islamic and rather against the very spirit of the structure of Islamic thought. The action of the Perfect Man persuades him to be divine and acquire the attributes of Allah Almighty. The Perfect Man needs the power to change History and society. As long as the Perfect man has to be in the image of God, he will have to acquire all the characteristics of God; and among these qualities, power is an important attribute. Differentiating between the Christian and the Muslim God, Iqbal describes, "Christianity describes God as love; Islam as power. How shall we decide between the two conceptions? I think the history of mankind and the universe as a whole must tell us as to which of the two conceptions is truer. I find that God reveals Himself in history more as power than love. I do not deny the love of God; I mean that based on our historical experience, God is better described as power"ⁱⁱⁱ. Iqbal further says, "Power is more divine than truth. God is power. Be ye then like your father who is in heaven"^{iv}. Thus, 'the powerful man creates environments, the feeble have to adjust themselves to it'.^v But this power is based upon Islamic morality. Iqbal says civilization is a thought of the powerful man".^{vi} And power has great potentialities, "Power touched falsehood and it is transformed into truth"^{vii}

Iqbal's attitude, it is to be noted, towards the application of power is very realistic. He does believe, of course, very firmly in the use of power but honestly and truthfully. He does not advocate the use of power in a ruthless way like Nietzsche. On the contrary, his Perfect Man is an upright, honest and truthful man. He hates immoral attitudes. The Perfect Man believes in the renunciation of desire. Unlike Christian monasticism, he lives in society and participates actively. He remains in society but still, he has a detached attitude. A Christian monk adopts a life of complete renunciation. A follower of Buddhist philosophy does not have any desire as this is the cause of real suffering. But the Perfect Man, on the one hand, does not have material desires; on the other hand, he has a desire for spiritual, metaphysical, and sophisticated unification. Hindu philosophers believe in the cyclic movement of life; Yogis believe in the concept of oneness with the Infinite Intelligence or God or Energy Shakti, Buddhists believe in the complete achievement of Nothingness- Iqbal, differing from all of them, believes in a conscious unification with God. Iqbal asserts that individual consciousness should be maintained in all conditions. The experience of reality creates such ecstasy that the individual wants to forget himself completely in God. On the contrary, Iqbal points out, that one should absorb and assimilate the reality in one's self instead of losing one's consciousness or individuality. Man is the vicegerent of God and without individual consciousness, he is incapable of any experience. A Perfect Man is supposed to acquire the attributes of God so writes the Holy Quran. Thus the Perfect Man should acquire Godly qualities in such a way that he still maintains his consciousness apart from the Overall Consciousness of God. Nicholson commenting upon this aspect of Iqbal's philosophy says:

"The moral and religious ideal of man is not self-negation but self-affirmation and he attains to this ideal by becoming more and more individual, more and more unique. The Prophet said, '*Takhallaque-bi-akhlaq Allah*, create in yourselves the attributes of God'. Thus man becomes unique by becoming more and more like the most unique Individual."^{viii} Maintenance of individuality is a very important characteristic of Iqbal's perfect man. This is a Quranic and Islamic concept. An individual should exclusively maintain his entity and identity. For Europe, these concepts may be new but in Islam, it is pointed out in the Holy Quran. There is an old confrontation between Intellect and Intuition. Philosophers believe in the supremacy of intellect and as a result, they have acute differences among themselves. They all disagree with one another but dedicatedly agree on one single point intellect is limited and incapable of creating. Moreover, it cannot lead to reality and cannot prove the existence of God. On the other hand, those who believe in the supremacy of institutions, they experience reality and therefore complement one another. Iqbal believed that as Spirit is the higher form of matter, in the same manner, Intuition is the higher form of Intellect. Both are important, when matter and intellect are liberated from the shackles of time and Space then they are transformed into Spirit and Intuition respectively. Thus both the aspects are important in their respective contexts.

Human personality is multi-dimensional. Iqbal has perceived the human self in its totality from the Quranic perspective. A Perfect Man is capable of transcending his being and there he experiences reality. This is an individual experience. The austere believers of the superiority of human intellect try to experience ultimate reality with this limited tool and are disappointed. As a result, they deny the existence of God. They want to

prove the existence of God with the help of reason while it is not possible. This can be experienced with the help of intuition by individuals and its collective experience is precarious.

Intellect is a slow-moving insect while Intuition believes in simple but rapidly emphatic action. Iqbal's Perfect Man makes use of all the two faculties but the main emphasis is, no doubt, on the supremacy of Intuition.

بے ذوق تجلی بھی اس خاک میں پنہاں غافل! تو ترا صاحب ادراک نہیں۔

The delight of manifestation is also hidden in this very matter.

O inattentive! thou art not the wielder of perception only!^{ix}

The development of the ego is an extremely important characteristic of the Perfect Man of Iqbal. The development of the individual Ego enables one to realize one's position on earth and determine one's locale, and status in this great ever-expanding universe of God. With the help of the agency of Ego, he achieves union with God, while, at the same time, maintaining his consciousness. Life is individuality and its supreme form is Ego which comprehends the totality

of Man's being. But this self-contained totality should be as akin to God as possible, Perfect Individual and among human beings, Muhammad (peace be upon him) is most perfect and manifests divine attributes. Therefore, he is the best example of perfection among human beings. The nearness of God and the Prophet (PBUH) makes the individual more complete, unique, and practical paragon of real manhood.

The development of the individual ego takes the individual to such close vicinity to God that they both become almost identical. Man is not lost in the identity of God but he imbibes and absorbs the attributes of God in his Ego. A Perfect Man can absorb the entire universe in his being. Iqbal writes about Mansoor Hallaj in this connection:

The development of this experience in the religious life of Islam reached its culmination in the well-known words of Hallaj-I am the creative truth. The contemporaries of Hallaj, as well as his successors, interpreted those words pantheistically but the fragments of Hallaj, collected and published by the French Orientalist, M. Massignon leave no doubt that the martyr saint could not have meant to deny the transcendence of God. The true interpretation of his experience, therefore, is not the drop slipping into the sea, but the realization and bold affirmation in an undying phrase of the reality and permanence of the human ego in a profound personality. "^x

Hence Nicholson explains that: The true person not only absorbs the world of matter; by mastering it he absorbs God Himself into his Ego. Life is a forward assimilative movement. It removes all obstructions in its march by assimilating them."^{xi}

Ego is the central pivot in the human personality which is a state of tension and progress is possible only when this tension is suspended and maintained. The Ego passes through three stages in its process of development. Obedience to the Law.

The following verses of Iqbal illumine this quality:

"By Obedience, the man of no worth is made worthy: By disobedience, his fire is turned to ashes."

"Who so would master the sun and stars, Let him make {himself a prisoner of Law!"

"Since Law makes everything strong within, why dost thou neglect this source of strength?"

Iqbal points out the benefits one gets by exercising self-control

He that does not command himself becomes a receiver of commands from others, Fasting assaults hunger and thirst and breaches the citadel of sensuality.^{xii}

The Perfect Man enjoys innumerable assets, God's vicegerent is as the soul of the universe; His being in the shadow of the Greatest Name." His genius abounds with life and desires to manifest itself, He will bring another world into existence."

He wakes and sleeps for God alone."

"He bestows life by his miraculous actions,
He renovates old ways of life.
Splendid visions rise from the print of his foot.
Many a Moses is entranced by his Sinai.
He gives a new explanation of Life,
A new interpretation of this dream.
His hidden being is Life's mystery,
The unheard music of Life's harp."^{xiii}

Apart from these three stages, certain factors fortify Ego. The element of Ishq' or Love plays a highly significant and profound role in the realization of the experience of the Ultimate Reality. Ego is strengthened with Love. It activates the creative process. Iqbal has written many verses about the concept of Love. It is difficult to define because it is an experience. It is difficult to define because it is an experience. Its effectiveness can be understood from some verses:

قوت عشق سے ہر پست کو بالا کر دے دہر میں اسم محمد ﷺ سے اجالا کر دے^{xiv}

With the force of Love elevate all objects

Enlighten the world with the name of Muhammad Peace Be Upon Him.

بے ابد کے نسخہ دیرینہ کی تمہید عشق عقل انسانی بے فغانی زندہ جاوید عشق^{xv}

"Love is the preamble of the prescription of eternity

Human intelligence is mortal and love is immortal.^{xvi}

مرد خدا کا عمل عشق سے صاحب فروغ عشق ہے اصل حیات، موت ہے اس پر حرام^{xvii}

The action of the man of God is the progress of Love

Love is the real essence of life and death is annulled for it.

جہاں میں لذت پرواز حق نہیں اس کا وجود نہیں جس کا جذب خاک سے آزاد^{xviii}

He has no right to enjoy the delight of flight

Who has not freed himself from the bondage of material?

The perfect man is to develop supreme encouragement and he is not afraid of anything. God is always for him. But his courageous actions are within the limits defined by the Holy Quran and the true man always obeys God only;

پیری میں فقیری میں شاہی میں غلامی میں کچھ کام نہیں بنتا ہے جرات رندانہ^{xix}

“In wealthiness humanity sovereignty and servitude,

Nothing can be done without dissolute courage.

افلاک سے ہے اس کی حریفانہ کشائش خاکی ہے مگر خاک سے آزاد ہے مومن

With skies, he has the anatomization of the opponents

Momin though belongs to earth but he is at the same free from it.

For a proper precaution of the nature of State and Law in Islam, it is the most beautiful known relationship in this universe. Allah says to refer to the basic Islamic concept. There is between Allah and man then necessary to refer to basic Islam. Allah Himself has a great love for man, much more than that of his mother, and has created man so that he may attain a supreme destiny by accepting man as His abid, Allah has promised to grant all protections and help to a man in the achievement of his goal. The bilateral primordial Allah's creation, Allah says he has created man in the best of mould, has made of his mother, and tenant exists between Allah and the whole of His creation, but man is the head of man His vicegerent on earth, has breathed His own spirit into him, has conferred honour on him, and has created all that is in the earth for him. But there is a difference between man and the rest of the creation. Allah commands it but man, though morally bound by his covenant to obey. The rest of the creation must Allah, may not obey Him. He has been granted the option to obey or not to obey. A man was to obey Allah alone, and to disobey all others the result would be that Allah would have to establish His own kingdom on earth and to enforce His own law. Every Government demands obedience from the people and promulgates its own laws, Therefore, if either the State was not provided by Allah or Laws were allowed to be provided by human beings then State not beings then So Allah sent His own representatives to the earth who are called Prophets. While man would be obeying someone other than Allah and this was not permissible. While on the one hand they were to preach to the people to obey Allah and to avoid the denying. They were at the same to establish the kingdom of Allah amongst people to whom they had been sent. It had been made clear that other than Allah that demands obedience from man. It had been made clear in by Allah that all these Prophets were entitled to obedience, though, of course. They had also to bring Codes for the lives of the human-beings for man had been sent to trial as to whether obeys Allah. Their capacity as representatives of Allah. They had also to bring Codes for the forced to accept the faith brought by a Prophet. That would defeat the establishment of Allah's kingdom did not at all mean that any person to that would defeat the purpose for which man had been sent to this world because man was on his trial. However, Allah had also to establish, whether he obeyed Allah of his own accord, However, Allah had also to establish the justice bet when man and man and to that extent force was also to be used by Prophets. The only just government is Allah's government. Every government in man over man was unjust. In fact, to subordinate man to man is an injustice in itself. Every person who is subjected to injustice has a right to be protected and therefore, the Prophets were fully justified in imposing the government of Allah even by force.

Conclusion

The debate is concluded, to sum up, that Iqbal advised that a perfect man is a true Muslim. He explained that a true Man will always obey God and His prophets. He always avoids fear, beggary, and slavery. This type of man always loves Allah Almighty. Such a person is not God-fearing and worldly-minded, and his ego is attached only to God. Such a person makes himself a fana Fi-Allah and this is the secret to his success.

من تو شدم تو من شدى، من تن شدم تو جاں شدى
تا کس نہ گوید بعد ازین، من دیگرم تو دیگرى

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